

Management

DUAL FACTOR THEORY OF JOB SATISFACTION: A REPLICATION IN LEATHER INDUSTRY IN TAMIL NADU

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.151694

ABSTRACT

As Frederick Herzberg noted in his 1968 article, “what has been unraveled [about the psychology of motivation] with any degree of assurance is small indeed. Herzberg believed that organizations have only limited power to motivate employees. Managers should make sure their incentive systems function reasonably well but should concentrate on enriching the work. There are down to earth managers who shout, “Kick the person!” And this type of manager is right. The surest and least difficult way of getting someone to do something is to administer a kick in the pants - to give what might be called the KITA(Kick in ask). This opened up the field of communications, a new area of “scientifically” sanctioned KITA.

Keywords:

Negative Physical KITA, Negative Psychological KITA, Negative KITA & Positive KITA.

Cite This Article: Dr. A. Thirupathy, “DUAL FACTOR THEORY OF JOB SATISFACTION: A REPLICATION IN LEATHER INDUSTRY IN TAMIL NADU”, International Journal of Research – Granthaalayah, Vol. 4, No. 9: SE (2016): 74-81.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ever since Elton Mayo conducted his famous Hawthorne experiments-in which factory workers’ productivity rose when lights were turned up, researchers have been struggling to fathom workplace motivation. It’s a slippery topic. That’s still true 35 years later, but we must endeavor to understand motivation better because it’s so central to organizational success.

When Frederick Hertzberg researched the contents of employee motivation during the 1950s and 1960s, he discovered a dichotomy that stills intrigues managers: The factors that make people satisfied and motivated on the job are different in kind from the things that make them dissatisfied.

Ask workers what makes them unhappy at work, and you'll hear about an angry boss, a low salary, an uncomfortable work space, or stupid rules. Managed badly, environmental factors make people miserable, and they can certainly be demotivating. But even if managed brilliantly, they don't motivate anybody to work much harder or smarter. People are motivated, instead, by interesting work, challenge, and increasing responsibility. These intrinsic factors answer people's deep-seated need for growth and achievement.

Hertzberg's work influenced a generation of academics and practitioners-but his conclusions don't seem to have being accepted by the executives as the capitations of the industry and service sectors still believe in pay as the motivator.

What has been known is very small in the complex field of psychology of motivation. In spite of thin line between knowledge and speculation in this branch, many attempts have been made to understand the phenomena.

WORK MOTIVATION

The simple way of getting some are to do something is to ask the person to do the job. But if the person responds that he or she does not want to do it, then that calls for psychological consultation to determine the reason for such obstinacy. Tell the person? The response shows that he or she does not understand you, and now an expert in communication methods has to be brought in to show you how to get through. Alternatively, give the person a monitory incentive. There is complexity and difficulty involved in setting up and administering an incentive system. Moreover, are not sure it works. Show the person? This means a costly training program. We need a simple way.

Negative Physical KITA This is a literal application of the term and was frequently used in the past. It has, however, three major drawbacks:

- It is inelegant;
- It contradicts the precious image of benevolence that most organizations cherish; and
- Since it is a physical attack, it directly stimulates the autonomic nervous system, and this often results in negative feedback-the employee may just kick you in return. These factors give rise to certain taboos against negative physical KITA.

In uncovering infinite sources of psychological vulnerabilities and the appropriate methods to play tunes on them, psychologists have come to the rescue of those who are no longer permitted to use negative physical KITA. "He took my rug away"; "I wonder what she meant by that"; "The boss is always going around me"-these symptomatic expressions of ego sores that have been rubbed raw are the result of application of negative physical KITA.

Negative Psychological KITA This has several advantages over negative physical KITA

- First, the cruelty is not visible; the bleeding is internal and comes much later.
- Second, since it affects the higher cortical centers of the brain with its inhibitory powers, it reduces the possibility of physical back-lash.
- Third, since the number of psychological pains that a person can feel is almost infinite, the direction and site possibilities of the KITA are increased many times.

- Fourth, the person administering the kick can manage to be above it all and let the system accomplish the dirty work.
- Fifth, those who practice it receive some ego satisfaction (one-upmanship), whereas they would find drawing blood abhorrent. Finally, if the employee does complain, he or she can always be accused of being paranoid; there is no tangible evidence of an actual attack.

Now, what does negative KITA accomplish? If a manager kicks an employee in the rear (physically or psychologically), who is motivated? The manager is motivated get employee moves Negative KITA does not lead to motivation, but to movement.

Positive KITA This is supposed to be one type of motivation. If a managers says to an employee, “Do this for me or the company, and in return I will give you a reward, an incentive, more status, a promotion, all the quid pro quos that exist in the industrial organization,” is the manager motivating the employee? The general opinion is that, “Yes, this is motivation.”

In recent times, several motivational techniques have been employed. A brief description is presented below:

REDUCING TIME SPENT AT WORK

This represents a marvelous way of motivating people to work - getting then of the job! The time spent on the job has been reduced. An interesting variant of the approach is the development of off-hour recreation programs. The philosophy here seems to be that those who play together work together. The fact is that motivated people seek more hours of work, not fewer.

SPIRALING WAGES

Have these motivated people? Yes, to seek the next wage increase. Some still can be heard to say that a good depression will make employees moving. They feel that if is wages don't or won't do the job, reducing them will.

FRINGE BENEFITS

Industry has out-beaten welfare States in dispensing cradle-to-the-grave succor. The cost of fringe benefits in the US has reached approximately 25% of the wage bill a still is crying for motivation.

People spend less time working for more money and more security than ever before, and the trend cannot be reversed. These benefits are no longer rewards; they are rights. A 6-day week is inhuman, a 10-hour day is exploitation, extended medical coverage is a basic decency, and stock options are the salvation of corporate initiatives. Unless the ante is continuously raised, the psychological reaction of employees is that the company is turning back the clock.

When industry began to realize that both the economic nerve and the lazy nerve of their employees had insatiable appetites, it started to listen to the behavioral scientists who, more out

of a humanist tradition than from scientific study, criticized management for not knowing how to deal with people. The next KITA easily followed.

HUMAN RELATIONS TRAINING

More than 30 years of practicing psychological approaches to handling people have resulted in costly human relations programs and, in the end, the same question: How do you motivate workers? Here, too, escalations have taken place. Thirty years ago it was necessary to request, "Please don't spit on the floor." Today the same admonition requires three "pleases" before the employee feels that a superior has demonstrated the psychologically proper attitude.

The failure of human relations training to produce motivation led to the conclusion that supervisors or managers themselves were not psychologically true to themselves in their practice of interpersonal decency. So an advanced form of human relations KITA, sensitivity training, was unfolded.

SENSITIVITY TRAINING

Do you really, really understand yourself? Do you really, really trust other people? Do you really, really cooperate? The failure of sensitivity training is now being explained, by those who have become opportunistic exploiters of the technique, as a failure to really (five times) conduct proper sensitivity training courses.

With the realization that there are only temporary gains from comfort and economic and interpersonal KITA, personnel managers concluded that the fault lay not in what they were doing, but in the employee's failure to appreciate what they were doing. This opened up the field of communications, a new area of "scientifically" sanctioned KITA.

TWO-WAY COMMUNICATION

Management ordered morale surveys, suggestion plans, and group participation programs. Then both management and employees were communicating and listening to each other more than ever without much improvement in motivation.

The behavioral scientists began to take another look at their conceptions and their data, and they took human relations one step further. A glimmer of truth was beginning to show through the writings of the so-called higher-order-need psychologists. People, so they said, want to actualize themselves. Unfortunately, the "actualizing" psychologists got mixed up with the human relations psychologists, and a new KITA emerged.

JOB PARTICIPATION

Though it may not have been the theoretical intention, job participation often became a "give them the big picture" approach. For example, if a man is tightening 10,000 nuts a day on an assembly line with a wrench, tell him he is building a Chevrolet. Another approach had the goal of giving employees a "feeling" that they are determining, in some measure, what they do on the

job. The goal was to provide a sense of achievement rather than a substantive achievement in the task. Real achievement, of course, requires a task that makes it possible.

But still there was no motivation. This led to the inevitable conclusion that the employees must be sick, and therefore to the next KITA.

EMPLOYEE COUNSELING

The initial use of this form of KITA in a systematic fashion can be credited to the Hawthorne experiment of the Western Electric Company during the early 1930s. At that time, it was found that the employees harbored irrational feelings that were interfering with the rational operation of the factory. Counseling in this instance was a means of letting the employees unburden themselves by talking to someone about their problems. Although the counseling techniques were primitive, the program was large indeed.

The counseling approach suffered as a result of experiences during World War II, when the programs themselves were found to be interfering with the operation of the organizations; the counselors had forgotten their role of benevolent listeners and were attempting to do something about the problems that they heard about. Psychological counseling, however, has managed to survive the negative impact of World War II experiences and today is beginning to flourish with renewed sophistication. But, alas, many of these programs, like all the others, do not seem to have lessened the pressure of demands to find out how to motivate workers.

Since KITA results only in short-term movement, it is safe to predict that the cost of these programs will increase steadily and new varieties will be developed as old positive KITAs reach their satiation points.

TWO FACTOR THEORY OF MOTIVATION

The two factor theory of motivation hypothesized the following

- Job satisfaction and job dissatisfaction are not two sides of the same coin, rather they are viewed as two separated matters.
- The opposite of job satisfaction is no job satisfaction and the opposite of job dissatisfaction is no job dissatisfaction.
- Job satisfaction is determined by the feeling that the individual has concerning the content of his job. These include task achievement, recognition, intrinsic interest in the task, increased task responsibility, advancement and occupational growth. They are called 'satisfiers'.
- These satisfiers serve to provide for the higher order needs of the human beings and to exercise one's capabilities as an instrumentality for psychological growth, and are also called 'motivators'.
- Job dissatisfaction is determined by the feelings the individual has concerning the context of his job. These include company policy and administration, technical supervision, working conditions, pay, interrelations with supervisors, subordinates and peers and job security,

- These dissatisfies serve to provide for the animal side of the man's nature, which needs to avoid unpleasant environment and are called 'hygiene's'.

HYGIENE VS. MOTIVATORS

This theory tries to answer the perennial question: How to install a generator in an employee?' A brief review of motivation-hygiene theory of job attitudes is required before theoretical and practical suggestions can be offered. The theory was first drawn from an examination of events in the lives of engineers and accountants. At least 16 other investigations, using a wide variety of populations (including some in the communist countries), have since been completed, making the original research one of the most replicated studies in the field of job attitudes.

2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Hertzberg's theory and study fired the imagination of a generation of scholars and executives. However, his conclusions and psycho philosophical underpinnings do not seem to have percolated to Indian organizations. Indian executives still pay attention to compensation and perks of their employees.

There is a need to investigate the extent to which this theory holds well in Indian context. To be sure there have been some replications of the original research work in India. However, no replication is done taking blue collar employees as sample. This study is an attempt in this direction. It fills the gap in the existing knowledge.

This research in initiated to seek answers to the question of work motivation and job satisfaction based on job attitudes of the employees in tanneries and shoe units located in Tamil Nadu. Using Hertzberg's original methodology high feelings and low feelings of the blue collar employees were ascertained to test the hypotheses.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Basically this study is designed to replicate Hertzberg's original research work in Indian contest using blue collar workers as subjects. Specifically the study is made with the following objectives.

To test the hypothesis that positive feeling lead to job satisfaction and negative feelings lead to job dissatisfaction.

To examine the impact of positive feeling on performance, turnover, attitude toward the company, mental health effects, and interpersonal relationships.

4. METHODOLOGY

This study used the same methodology as used by Hertzberg's and his associates. The critical incident method was used to understand the high feeling or low feeling about the job. Five hundred blue collar employees of leather industries situated in Tamil Nadu were the subjects of

study. A translated version of the interview schedule of Herzberg's study was used to ascertain positive and negative job attitudes and answer were also recorded in Tamil.

In addition to job attitudes information about the impact of job satisfaction on turnover, health, quality and quantity of production was also collected.

The interpretation of the data was done by two experts to avoid bias of the researcher. The critical incidents were analyzed by the experts.

The schedules as well as the answer sheet were given to the two senior researcher of the department for the codification. Percentage analysis method was used for interpretation of the results.

5. RESULTS

The following hypothesized have been conformed in this study

- Factor which are reasonable for job dissatisfaction are different from the factor leading to job satisfaction.
- Achievement, recognition, advancement, works itself, possibility of growth, and responsibility will lead to job motivation.
- Factor like lack of company policy and administration, poor quality of supervisions, bad relationship with supervisors, peer subordinates, poor pay, job security, lack of person working conditions, and low status, lead to job satisfaction and provision of this factor do not lead to motivation.
- Job satisfaction predicts performance effects, turnover, attitude toward the company, mental-health effects, and interpersonal relationships.

6. LIMITATIONS

The main limitation of the study is its sample, i.e. blue collar workers and no attempt is made to replicate the study among white collar employees. Therefore the findings are like to hold good for blue collar employees.

Due to scarcity of funds as well as time at the disposal of the researcher, the study is confined to one industry in India. It would have been more meaningful of investigation is made covering all the industries and service sector units across the length and breadth of India.

7. CONCLUSION

Now the question that arises is what the managements of industry which employs blue collar workers has to do for improving motivational levels? This job enrichment mechanism presented is influenced by Herzberg's formulations.

Managements of these industrial undertakings should provide in the jobs an opportunity to the employees to grow and make personal contributions to their jobs.

The following gives the principles and Motivators.

8. PRINCIPLES AND MOTIVATORS

PRINCIPLES

- While retaining accountability some control need to be removed.
- Increasing the accountability of employees.
- Empowering employees by assigning total works.
- Giving freedom of job.
- Providing feedback to employees themselves rather than to supervisor.
- Challenging task.
- Giving employee's specific task to become expert.

MOTIVATORS

- Achievement and responsibilities.
- Responsibilities and recognition.
- Recognition, achievement and responsibilities.
- Recognition, achievement and responsibilities.
- Recognition.
- Achievement.
- Responsibility growth and advancement.

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